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CAUSE ADVERTISING FOR AN EFFECTIVE CONTROL OF THE HABIT OF TOBACCO CONSUMPTION: AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract

Purpose- is to examine as to how inner conflict of consumers can be used as a tool of behavioral modifier for an effective societal advertising.

Design/methodology/approach- Primary focus is on examining the role of conflict in prompting rationalization that keeps habitual behavior intact and the role of high potency information in blocking rationalization. It further investigates place of advertising media in this respect from a different perspective.

Findings- It is found that people are more likely to incline towards rationalization than to refrain from it in normal state of conflict. Blocking undue and unnecessary rationalizations may help to reach useful behavioral modifications like tobacco consumption. It is found that high potential cognitive conflict have the clout to block such undue rationalization. Strategic designing of anti tobacco advertising campaign has a definite role in this regard.

Originality/Value- majority of anti-tobacco campaign focus on information regarding risk associated with this habit and raise only mild conflict among the tobacco users. This type of conflict finds rationalizations as easy escape-route. This aborts the objectives of the campaign. Only high potency conflict can block rationalization that leads to favorable resolution. In the present study this fact has been tried to be established using a specific research design

Keywords- Cause Advertising, High Potency Conflict, Consumers' Dissonance, Rationalization, Resolution.

INTRODUCTION:

Advertising is an important way of contest in industries that are highly intense, such as the cigarette industry. A highly concentrated industry is characterized by a small number of relatively large firms. Firms in industries of this type tend not to contend by price, but try to boost sales with advertising. According to *Becker and Murphy (1993)*, advertising is an information complement to the good itself. Cigarette advertising is not designed to convey information about the material characteristics of the product. Information about this uniqueness is easily obtained. Cigarette advertising is designed to create a fantasy of erudition, delight, and social sensation. This becomes the product 'personality', which the advertisers expect will plea to specific segments of the market. In developing countries, this imagery can be designed to associate the product with a stunning fantasy of American or European life-styles. The relatively small expenditure on tobacco provides a bond to this fantasy life-style. If tobacco advertising and promotion increase tobacco consumption, they are public health issues. Although public health advocates (*Roemer, 1993*) claim that tobacco advertising and promotion do increase cigarette consumption, there is a significant empirical literature that finds no effect of tobacco advertising on smoking (*Duffy, 1996*) and there is very little empirical research on other promotional activities. The empirical literature on advertising provides the basis for the tobacco industry's claim that its advertising only affects market share between various competing brands. Therefore, there are conflicting evidences in support and against the proposition that advertising in cigarette industry does exhort smokers. This debate needs some deeper enquiry.

REVIEW OF EXISTING LITERATURE:

Prior empirical studies of the effects of advertising on tobacco consumption

Study	Topic	Conclusion
Time series studies		
Hamilton (1972)	Advertising, the health scare, and the cigarette advertising ban.	No effect of advertising
Grabowski (1976)	The effect of advertising on the inter-industry distribution of demand	No effect of advertising
Schmalensee (1972)	<i>On the Economics of Advertising</i> . Amsterdam: North Holland	No effect of advertising
Schneider <i>et al.</i> (1981)	Government regulation of cigarette health information.	No effect of advertising
Baltagi & Levin (1986)	Estimating dynamic demand for cigarettes using panel data: the effects of Bootlegging, taxation, and advertising reconsidered.	No effect of advertising
Johnson (1986)	Advertising expenditure and the aggregate demand for cigarettes in Australia.	No effect of advertising.
Porter (1986)	The impact of government policy on the US cigarette industry. In <i>Empirical Approaches to Consumer Protection Economics</i>	No effect of advertising
Wilcox & Vacker (1992)	Cigarette advertising and consumption in the United States.	No effect of advertising
Duffy (1995)	Advertising in demand systems for alcoholic drinks and tobacco: a comparative study.	No effect of advertising
Valdes (1993)	Cigarette consumption in Spain: empirical evidence and implications for public Health policy.	Small positive effect of advertising
Chetwynd <i>et al.</i> (1988)	Impact of cigarette advertising on aggregate demand for cigarettes in New	Small positive effect of advertising

	Zealand.	
McGuinness & Cowling (1975)	Advertising and the aggregate demand for cigarettes.	Small positive effect of advertising
Seldon & Doroodian (1989)	A simultaneous model of cigarette advertising: effects on demand and industry response to public policy.	Small positive effect of advertising
Cross-sectional studies		
Lewit <i>et al.</i> (1981)	The effects of government regulation on teenage smoking.	Positive effect of advertising
Goel & Morey (1995)	The interdependence of cigarette and liquor demand.	Positive effect of advertising
Roberts & Samuelson (1988)	An empirical analysis of dynamic, non price competition in an oligopolistic industry.	Positive effect of advertising
Counter-advertising studies		
Schneider <i>et al.</i> (1981)	Government regulation of cigarette health information.	Negative effect of counter-advertising
Lewit <i>et al.</i> (1981)	The effects of government regulation on teenage smoking.	Negative effect of counter-advertising
Porter (1986)	The impact of government policy on the US cigarette industry. In <i>Empirical Approaches to Consumer Protection Economics</i>	Negative effect of counter-advertising
Hu <i>et al.</i> (1995)	Reducing cigarette consumption in California: tobacco taxes vs. an anti-smoking media Campaign.	Negative effect of counter-advertising
Pierce <i>et al.</i> (1990)	Long-term effectiveness of mass media led antismoking campaigns in Australia.	Negative effect of counter-advertising
Pekurinen (1989)	The demand for tobacco products in Finland.	Negative effect of counter-advertising
Flay (1987)	Mass media and smoking cessation: a critical review.	Negative effect of counter-advertising
Goldman & Glantz (1998)	Evaluation of antismoking advertising campaigns	Negative effect of counter-advertising
Baltagi & Levin (1986)	Estimating dynamic demand for cigarettes using panel data: the effects of bootlegging, taxation, and advertising reconsidered.	Negative effect of counter-advertising

The first group of studies reviewed is those using national-aggregate advertising data as the measure of advertising. The industry-level response function presented above suggests that this type of study will not find any effect of advertising. There will be no effect found since the level of cigarette advertising is relatively high and national level data may not provide sufficient variance to find out any effect. *Schmalensee (1972)* and *Duffy (1996)* make the out of the ordinary and almost universally ignored point that a study of cigarette advertising should control for changes in the level of advertising in all industries. The level of advertising in all industries is defined as external advertising. All the above mentioned cigarette advertising expenditure studies that use national, annual, or quarterly time-series data. As expected, find either no effect or a small effect of advertising on cigarette demand. *Chetwynd et al. (1988)* find a small effect with quarterly data that is lost when aggregation is increased to the annual level. This supports the theory that annual data have too little variance for effects to be detected. *Duffy (1996)* reviews these studies and a few more that also use national level advertising data. He also reports that these studies find either no effect or a small effect and concludes that these studies show that cigarette advertising has no effect on cigarette consumption. An unconventional conclusion, as eminent by *Warner et*

al. (1986), is that studies which use a single time-series of national-level data are inappropriate to measure the effect of advertising on consumption.

The second category of studies includes those that measure advertising at a local cross-sectional level. There are only three studies that use cross-sectional data. The reason for their scarcity is that the data are expensive and tricky to assemble. The study by Roberts and *Samuelson (1988)* is somewhat different, but may still be classified as cross-sectional. In the study the cross-sectional unit is the firm. These authors conclude that advertising increases market size, and that market share is related to the number of brands. They show that when advertising is measured over a wide range, such as with cross-sectional data, a significant positive effect of advertising is observed.

The third category of advertising studies includes those that examine the effect of Counter-advertising on consumption. This type of study is likely to find a significant relationship and, in fact, a considerable number do find that counter-advertising reduces consumption. *Warner (1981)*, *Lewit et al. (1981)*, *Schneider et al.(1981)*, and *Baltagi & Levin (1986)*, all included measures of counter-advertising, and all concluded that counter-advertising was effective in reducing cigarette consumption. Tobacco control in developing countries is greater than the positive effect of their advertising. The cigarette companies gave up broadcast advertising so that they would not have to fund more counter-advertising. A series of local counter-advertising campaigns has also been analyzed. A study by *Pierce et al. (1990)* finds that counter-advertising reduced smoking in two Australian cities. *Hu et al. (1995)* find that counter-advertising reduced smoking in California. *Goldman & Glantz (1998)* find that counter-advertising in California and Massachusetts reduced smoking. *Flay (1987)* reviews the results of local counter-advertising campaigns in Finland, the United Kingdom, Norway, Israel, Austria, and Canada, and concludes that counter-advertising is effective in reducing cigarette consumption.

The investigation of existing literature presented above offers a mixed bag of indications about the effectiveness of advertising in the promotion of tobacco/cigarette per se consumption in different parts of the world and the same with regard to the viability of counter advertising to control the consumption of the same. On average it appears that counter advertising has some definite effect in controlling the habit of using tobacco. Nonetheless, in developing countries where direct control is relatively more than the counter advertising posted less effective results and promotional advertising were found positive impact. This fact has been critically examined in different section of the present study.

What is behind this phenomenon?

Can we blame it on Rio! May be? It was all a humorous representation of human greed, cunningness; id, ego and super-ego conflicts and their different mix-ups were filmed in a cinema named 'Blame It On Rio' (i.e., Rio -de Jenero) where cheating, ditching, immoral and devious engagements of the filmed characters were blamed on to the Rio it self- a tourist destination in Brazil- where all the mishaps among them took place and captured. It was shown there that whatever are the temptations, good or bad, inside four walls of our consciousness, we always strive for even a temporary inner state of peace i.e., free from all sort of turmoil inside. We cannot live with our subtle state of conflict for long and whenever it comes across we try our best to deny it or disregard it or even try to shift it on to something else. Psychologists have defined it as an act of defense mechanism in the situations where a person find himself or herself in inner state of conflict and psychological mechanisms are applied to reduce anxiety arising out of such conflicts (*Freud, 1937; Cramer, 1991*). Defense mechanisms are unconscious mechanism aimed at reducing anxiety that arises from situations like when the id impulses are in conflict with each other, or when id impulses conflict with super-ego values and believes or even when an external threat is posed against to the ego. Two processes works within the phenomenon of Ego. First, unconscious process, that works where thought are not organized in a coherent way. No logic and no time line operate in opposition to this. There is a conscious secondary

process also which set strong boundaries and where thought must be organized in a coherent way. Cognition generally arise here but for the individual to function normally in the society impulses arising out of it must also respect reality of the world. However, when Id impulses are in conflict with super-ego the feelings of anxiety comes to the fore and often accompanied by the feeling of guilt, regret or even embarrassment. When anxiety or conflict becomes overwhelming it is then the ego employ defense mechanism to protect itself [22].

Important Defense Mechanism (DM) are identified as: Denial, Displacement, Intellectualization, Projection, Rationalization, Reaction formation, Regression, Repression, Sublimation, Suppression, Compensation, Dissociation , Fantasy, Identification, Undoing and Withdrawal(*Freud, 1937 ; Cramer ,1991*).

For the present study (with respect to tobacco/cigarette per se consumption) Projection, Rationalization (a process of constructing a logical justification for a decision to make excuses for once mistakes), Denial (denying the fact) are more relevant types.

Tobacco consumption is such an area of our social life where Anti –tobacco sentiments is strongly present as value recommendation and number of statutory provisions forwarded by public institutions along the side. It raises tension and conflict among the tobacco users. To reduce such conflict they usually follow different defense mechanism as mentioned above. Can the concept and the process of defense mechanism be itself being useful in controlling tobacco consumption? It is also a question as to how the Anti-Tobacco Campaign Advertising (ATCA) may be more effective tool using the same concept i.e., defense mechanism.

Researchers have tried hereunder to find out the prevailing Anti- tobacco Advertising and its limitations with regard to inducing fear and conflict that reduce tobacco consumption by blocking and weakening possible defense mechanism that tobacco consumers usually apply. We have also examined hypothesis which comprehend that a potent cognitive –emotive conflict can block harmful rationalization. Assuming this to be so, researchers have tried to analyze the design and contents of Anti -tobacco advertisement printed on product packets, pouches or sachets. At the last the researchers offered suggestions to improved the quality of advertisement in this regard.

For the purpose a flow diagram is developed that shows the structure & flow of conflict, rationalization, resolution and the modified consumer behavior. The whole assessment of the research problem is based on this flow diagram followed by the detail methodology that test hypotheses and signify the results.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

Consumers' cognitive-affective state of consciousness always found involved with series of evaluations to make subjective valuation of the things that matters to consumers or consumers' attachment with it. This process produces positive and negative attitudinal outcomes. The former is characterized with the state of inner satisfaction and the later one is supposed to accompany with the inner conflict in the consumers' mind. Consumers' inner conflict may be more or less depending upon the cognitive and emotive inputs. High cognitive-affective contents of stimuli and the corresponding negative evaluations in response to surrounding realities or information or ideas or even acts of consumption that leads to even higher level of inner conflict in consumers. The result of evaluation, i.e., positive and negative attitudinal outputs, in turn reflected in regrets. Regret demands way out to regain existing state of reprieve by the consumers that prompt consumers to search cognitive –affective solution to the problem. Literature on social psychology and human behavior claim that the search for cognitive-affective solution to the problem results in to two set of responses; one is rationalization and the second one is resolution for relinquishing existing habits. On average, it is found that people are more likely to incline towards rationalization than to refrain from it in normal state of cognitive-affective

evaluation of self image as well as self interest. Blocking undue and unnecessary rationalizations may help to reach useful behavioral modification including harmful habits like tobacco consumption.

(*paste Exhibit-1 here)

Question is whether this potential energy of conflict that pushes a person to try rationalization can also be used for blocking undue rationalization or can it be directed towards a resolution to quit or behavioral modification for the better.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The objective of the present work is to examine as to how inner conflict of consumers can be used as a tool of behavioral modifier for an effective cause advertising.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

The present study is confined in to only in Guwahati of Assam (India).

RESEARCH QUESTIONS:

In the present study we have tried to examine some basic questions relating to the assumptions made above. Questions are:

1. Why does rationalization arise?
2. Can rationalization be blocked?
3. Does an enlightened conflict blocks rationalization?
4. What happened when rationalization is blocked?

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY:

The hypotheses of the preset work are as follows:

H₀₁: Higher cognitive- emotive inputs do not create high level of inner conflict.

H₀₂: Higher inner conflict does not block and defuse easy rationalization

H₀₃: Blocked rationalization does not result in to behavioral modification.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

The present study covers conceptual investigation and empirical verification regarding the role of cognitive – affective contents of ad campaign in attaining behavioral modifications of consumers relating to injurious consumption of tobacco and tobacco containing products. The present relationship is investigated keeping in mind the impact of cognitive – affective evaluation fueled by cognitive inputs on inner conflicts in consumers when existing attachment towards life set up and expectations are challenged following the said evaluation. Primary focus is on examining the role of conflict, which is main source of rationalization that keeps habitual behavior intact, in blocking rationalization to allow the mental energy produced by the conflict to achieve favorable or intended behavioral modification among the targeted consumers.

Different research questions and hypotheses associated with the present study will be answered as well as be tested following the methodology given below:

1. Cognitive level of the respondents will be grouped in to two categories i.e., high and low, on the basis of the awareness level about the message & mark contained in an ad content.
2. Cognitive –affective evaluation level will be judged on the basis of quantity and intensity of arguments offered for and against the message & mark in an ad.
3. Level of conflict will be measured on the basis of sign of stress expressed in terms of tension, guilt, fear/scare and regret corresponding to contents imprinted in ads.

4. Level of rationalization will be measured on the basis of number of arguments offered in support to the respondents' attachment to the existing habits.
5. Correlation between 3 & 4 and Chi -square analysis of the same will show the existing relationship between conflict and rationalization.
6. Chi-square analysis of High (Low) correlation between conflict & rationalizations and high commitment (low commitment) for a quit will prove whether high level of conflict blocks rationalization or not.

Both primary and secondary sources of data were used for this purpose. Primary data were collected through structured schedule containing relevant questions. Total 250 copies of schedule were administered for collecting data. Out of that 54% were selected randomly using random table. Thereafter 136 were selected as final sample of data and remaining three were rejected on the basis of poor performance in this regard for a large number of questions were not responded. The respondents were selected on convenient basis at different locations of Guwahati covering all the six zones. The secondary data that were of great assistance extracted from the relevant research articles published in referred journals and downloads from electronic sources. Following this, based on the research queries in the present study, three null hypotheses were also formulated.

The data were systematically tabulated, edited and interpreted thereafter in order to make analysis and test hypotheses framed in the study. Statistical tools like percentage, measures of central tendency and correlation are done with in this piece of work.

ANALYSIS OF INFORMATION AND DATA:

Now we enter here into the analysis part of the present work where we have examined the work under the design of research questions and hypotheses. The guiding line would be the objective of the study with the help of methodology developed for the purpose.

*(paste table & figure 1 here)

The table -1 shows that 93% of the tobacco users recognize the warning where 7% of the total users fail to recognize the same.

*(paste table 2 & figure 2 here)

Table-2 shows that the most (58%) consumers were not aware about the warning message contained in the tobacco products. However, 42% could recognize the warning message which shows the awareness among the tobacco product users.

*(paste table 3 here)

As presented in the Table 3, it showed that the Users' age range between 15-20 and 40 years & above. It could be seen from the distribution that the maximum percentage of user lies in the age group between 21-25 years which is 23% of the total sample. The obvious implication of this finding is the dominance of youths in the market for the tobacco products.

*(paste figure 3 & table 4 here)

The reasons for using tobacco products by the consumers depicted in the Table-4 ranges from habit (35%) to better price (0%). Habit accounts (35%) and plays a major role in tobacco consumption among the users that makes relinquishment difficult for them.

*(paste Figure: 4 & Table 5 here)

When the users' responses were recorded and tabulated (given above) , it was found that the users felt stress in different form ranging from tension to guilt to fear/scare or even regret .

Maximum numbers of users were found feeling guilt which is 54% of the total sample size and next highest number was in the category of regret i.e., 25% of the total. The whole result was grouped in three levels of conflict: high, moderate and low. Within this classification percentage of respondents recorded in the high moderate and low levels were 33%, 54% and 13 % respectively. Obviously concentration is in the middle and the distribution is negatively skewed.

*(paste figure 5 here)

If we relate results with the problem associated with conflict relating to tobacco consumption the distribution, though negatively skewed, indicates supportive results for the anti tobacco campaign where 33 % respondents are in high conflict strata but the high concentration is in the middle. Therefore, the moderate level of conflict shifted center of gravity to the left that suppose to help the consumers to go for rationalization as defense mechanism to reduce the conflict and go Scott- free of their conscience pinching otherwise .

*(paste table 6 here)

Table: 6 above records some of the important reasons responsible for creating willingness of quitting tobacco consumption among the users. Here most responsible reason is fear of disease. Family pressure and concern for the family are secondary in effect ending with only 35% of the total.

*(figure-6 & table 7 here)

Table:7 reflects some of the important reasons offered as excuses for going with the existing habit of consuming tobacco despite the awareness about the dangers of consuming tobacco for long and the associated with it. Maximum weightage is on habit which is 35% of the total responses. The second highest percentage associated with excuse offered for the same is not much cases of disease and troubles were seen around which is 23% of the total responses. Little options and way outs were found third important excuse in this regard with a value of 12%. Some other minor excuses are: fake and fraudulent advertisement and non users' presence in the group of sufferers.

*(paste figure 7 here)

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION:

A. Findings: Important findings of the present study are discussed under different headings hereunder:

1. Objective of the present study which states as to how inner conflict of consumers can be used as a tool of behavioral modifier for an effective societal advertising with respect to the practice of tobacco consumption in India was examined with the help of Chi-square analysis of association between the levels of conflict and rationalization of respondents. The chi-square value here indicates that changing levels of conflict are significantly associated with the changing levels of rationalization and correlation value between the set of data points out that there is a negative correlation between higher to lower conflict levels and lower to higher rationalization levels. Combining two results together we conclude that high conflict has a role to control rationalization and that if rationalization can be blocked by virtue of high conflict level the potential energy of high conflict flows to strike some real solution in form of some positive behavioral modification.

*(paste table: 8&9 here)

2. On the basis or results and evidences presented above we can opine here that rationalization is a natural psychological defense mechanism that people practice when they

find themselves in conflict situation arising out of cognition and understanding about the unwanted realities of life situation or habit and the psychological attachment with things and dangers associated with it. Regarding harmful rationalization it is found that such rationalization can also be blocked by inducing high potency conflicts through strategic ad copy designing using science of consumer behavior and psychology, science and art of effective messaging and timing and quality of media application. It was also indicated that conflict that produces rationalization may also be used for blocking the same.

3. (i) *H₀₁: High cognitive- emotive inputs do not create high level of inner conflict.*

With reference to table -2 and table -5 it is clear that ratio of respondents in high awareness and high conflict level is higher than the ratio between low awareness levels. It indicates that the null hypothesis is rejected.

(ii) *H₀₂: High level of inner conflict of consumers does not block and defuse easy rationalization*

Results found in chi-square and correlation analyses rejects the null hypotheses and support the proposition that High level of inner conflict of consumers does block and defuse easy rationalization.

(iii) *H₀₃: Blocked rationalization does not result in to behavioral modification.*

*(Paste table 10 here)

The value of $r = 0.96$ indicates that there is high positive association between blocked rationalization and willingness for behavioral modification. Therefore, the null- hypotheses may be rejected and thus the inducement of high conflict - comfortably above a threshold limit – will be helpful in designing of an effective societal- advertising including the anti-tobacco campaign in the present case.

B. Conclusion:

Hence we can conclude that the research questions have answered according to the assumption made in the paper and all the null hypotheses claiming no relationship and significance of high potency conflicts to behavioral modifications were rejected that show that strategic advertising may support expected behavioral modification among the tobacco consumers if design and execution are on the expected line. Beside this the methodology proposed in the paper was also validated.

Therefore, contents and design of anti-tobacco advertising are key to its success. It must be capable of raising high potency conflict, regret, fear and guilt. Unfortunately, this has largely been either ignored or avoided in India. Danger mark and warning message are mostly failed to generate any material impact on consumers by failing to raise the level of conflict led by cognitive-emotive design of the tobacco consumers. Reasons may be –as examined above-weak impact generated by current ad campaign against the tobacco consumption in India. For example, that the mark usually used in anti-tobacco campaign in India i.e. scorpion is a commonly identified thing in our culture and comparatively carries low perceptual danger than many other symbols might have viz., skull or even fire of the last rites etc. These apart, grimy pictures of patients may be of a better option. These may be simply the speculative answers but still worth high for a serious throughput.

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APPENDIX

A. Tables And Figures

Table: 1; Recognition of the Warning Mark

Number of respondents		%
Yes	126	93
No	10	7
Total	136	100

Source: primary data

Figure: 1; Recognition of the warning mark

Source: primary data

Table: 2; Users Awareness about the Warning Message

Awareness level	Number	(%)
High	57	42
Low	79	58
Total	136	100

Source: primary data

Figure: 2; Users Awareness about the Warning Message

Source: primary data

Table: 3; Product Preference among the Users

Products	Age Group(in year) (Respondent in numbers)						%
	15- 20	21-25	26-30	31-35	36-40	41& above	
Cigarettes	9	25	13	10	13	9	29
Jorda paan	NA	18	10	13	11	NA	19
Khoini	NA	NA	9	14	9	11	16
Biri	NA	NA	8	NA	NA	10	7
Gutkha	11	19	16	17	14	NA	29
Total	20(8%)	62(23%)	56(21%)	54(20%)	47(17%)	30(11%)	100

Source: primary data

Figure: 3; Product Preference among the Users

Source: primary data

Table: 4; Reasons for Using the Product

Reasons	Age group (in year) (Number of respondents)						Percentage (%)
	Below 20	21-25	26-30	31-35	36-40	41& above	
Habit	10	23	16	18	16	11	35
Taste	NA	6	4	6	4	NA	8
Enjoyment	8	14	9	10	9	10	22
Refreshment	9	15	11	12	11	9	25
To give company to friends	NA	11	9	8	NA	NA	10
Better price	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	0
Total	27(10%)	69(26%)	49(18%)	54(20%)	40(15%)	30(11%)	100

Source: primary data

Figure: 4; Reasons for using the product

Source: primary data

Table- 5: Feelings after Visualizing the Warning Message/ Mark.

	Number of Respondents							
	Low Conflict			Moderate Conflict		High conflict		
	Tension	Nothing	Total	Guilt	Total	Fear/Scare	Regret	Total
	11	10	21	84	84	15	37	52
Percentage	7%	6%	13%	54%	54%	7%	25%	33%

Source: primary data

Figure- 5: Feelings after Visualizing the Warning Message/ Mark.

Source: primary data

Table-6: Reason for Willingness to Quit

Reasons	(Number of Respondents)	%
Family pressure	24	17%
Fear of disease	93	65%
For the benefit of the family	26	18%
Due to warning print on the product	NA	NA
Friends advise	NA	NA
Total	143	100

Source: primary data

Figure-6: Reason for Willingness to Quit

Source: primary data

Table -7: Reasons offered as an Excuse for Tobacco Consumption (Rationalization):

Level of willingness to Quit	Reasons	(Number of Respondents)	%
High	Very little option to switch over	20	12
	There are very few means & ways to quit	12	7
	Fake & fraudulent advertisement exploits the willing respondents	15	9
Total		47	28
Medium	Habitual matter difficult to leave.	59	35
	Not faced any such troubles worth mentioning	40	23
Total		99	58
Low	Non users are also suffering from cancer & other diseases	11	6
	No comments	14	8
Total		25	14
Grand Total		171	100

Source: primary data

Figure: 7, Reason for Willingness to Quit

Source: primary data

Table-8: Chi-square analysis of association ships between the levels of conflict and Rationalization of respondents

Conflict level Rationalization level	High conflict	Moderate conflict	Low conflict	Total
Low Rationalization	09(8.6)	10(14.3)	8(4.08)	27
Moderate Rationalization	38(18.81)	13(31.25)	8(8.93)	59
High Rationalization	12(31.57)	75(52.44)	12(14.98)	99
Total	59	98	28	185
X² (chi square value)= 57.84 significant at 4 d.f. & .0005 significance level				

Source: primary data

Table: 9; Correlation between levels of conflict and Rationalization of the respondents

Level of conflict	X (conflict)	Level of Rationalization	Y (Rationalization)	X²	Y²	XY
High	45	Low	14	2025	196	630
Medium	84	Medium	59	7056	3481	4956
Low	14	High	70	196	4900	980
Total	143	Total	143	9277	6722	6566
r = - .5197, n= 3 (Direction of the relationship is negative and as per the assumption made.)						

Source: primary data

Table-10: Correlation between levels of conflict – rationalization and the level of intension to Quit of the respondents

Level (power of conflict to block rationalization)	X (Conflict – Rationalization)	Level(intension to quit tobacco consumption)	Y (Quit)	X²	Y²	XY
High Conflict - Low Rationalization (high blockage of rationalization)	09	High intension to Quit	33	81	1089	297
Medium conflict – Medium Rationalization (Medium blockage of rationalization)	45	Medium intension to Quit	92	2025	8464	4140
Low conflict-Low Rationalization (Low blockage of rationalization)	12	Low intension to Quit	18	144	324	216
Total	66		143	2250	9877	4653
r= 0.96						

Source: primary data

B.

Exhibit: 1; structure of conflict resolution and the modified consumer behavior.

Source: Developed by Authors

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